

Effect of growth location on protein content of rice cultivar L202.

Sample	% N × 5.95 ^a
California (California seed)	9.4 a
Italy (California seed)	7.4 d
Spain (Spanish seed)	7.9 b
Italy (Spanish seed)	7.6 c

^a Values with different letters are statistically different at P < 0.05.

samples when acetic acid extracts were analyzed by aluminum lactate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (AL-PAGE) in 10% acrylamide gel.

Overall band intensity of the Italian samples (lanes II and IV in figure) was weaker than that of American and Spanish samples (lanes I and III). Patterns of Italian samples lacked one prominent band (a in figure). The patterns

of the American and Spanish samples were nearly the same; those of the Italian samples were identical.

Differences in the electrophoregrams may be related to the differences in cooking quality. Samples of a cultivar from different agroclimatic regions should be treated separately to maintain the uniqueness of a particular germplasm and/or quality characteristics. □

Milling recovery as influenced by different types of rice mills

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Machinery in milling affects the outturn of head rice and total rice. Using outmoded mills results in relatively higher quantitative and qualitative losses.

We compared different types of rice mills—stedhuller (Engelberg type), disc sheller (under-runner type), and modern rubber roller mill—to assess quantitative losses. Test varieties were KS282 (medium grain) and Basmati 385 (fine grain).

Effect of rice mills on milling recovery.^a

Mill type	Total milled rice (%)	Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)
<i>KS282</i>			
Steel huller	67.6 c	51.8 c	15.8 c
Disc sheller	70.0 b	56.2 b	13.8 b
Modern rubber roller	71.7 a	59.6 a	12.1 a
<i>Basmati 385</i>			
Steel huller	66.3 c	49.7 c	16.6 c
Disc sheller	69.0 b	54.0 b	15.0 b
Modern rubber roller	70.0 a	57.0 a	13.5 a

^a On a rough rice basis. Values with different letters are statistically different at P < 0.05 by DMRT.

The modern mill produced more head rice in the test varieties than did either the disc sheller or the steel huller (see table). Total milled rice percentage was also

higher with the modern mill. Different mills produced broken rice ranging from 12.1 to 15.8% for KS282 and 13.5 to 16.6% for Basmati 385. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Inheritance of resistance to rice stripe virus (RSV) in Yunnan Province, China

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We studied the inheritance of resistance to RSV in resistant foreign varieties Zhongguo 91, Fengfeng, and Tetep and native Chinese varieties Shuangfeng 1, Huxuan 19, and 683 Nuo.

Crosses were made in the fall of 1987. Parents, F₁, and F₂ were inoculated at the three-leaf stage with viruliferous small brown planthoppers during summer 1988.

Diseased plants and heart-withered shoots were counted after 25 d. Disease-free seedlings were planted in a field of a heavily diseased district,

Results at seedling and tillering stages were analyzed using a disease index where 0-29% was considered

resistant (R), 30-59% was moderately resistant (MR), and more than 60% was infected (S).

Zhongguo 91, Fengfeng, and Tetep were highly resistant to RSV; Huxuan 19, Shuangfeng 1, and 683 Nuo were moderately resistant. Resistance was

Table 1. Resistance to RSV of parents and F₁. Yunnan Province, China, 1988.

Parents and F ₁	Plants (no.)	Disease incidence (%)	Disease index (%)	Resistance
Zhongguo 91	174	6.9	6.1	R
Huxuan 19	182	40.1	31.9	MR
Shuangfeng 1	60	58.3	51.3	MR
Fengfeng	220	18.6	16.1	R
683 Nuo	190	56.8	48.0	MR
Tetep	96	14.6	10.8	R
Zhongguo 91/Huxuan 19	11	9.1	9.1	R
Huxuan 19/Zhongguo 91	18	5.6	5.6	R
Zhongguo 91/Shuangfeng 1	10	30.0	26.7	R
683 Nuo/Fengfeng	10	20.0	10.0	R
Huxuan 19/Fengfeng	19	26.3	26.3	R
Shuangfeng 1/Tetep	19	21.1	20.2	R

Table 2. Resistance to RSV of F₂. Yunnan Province, China, 1988.

Cross	F ₂ plants observed (no.)			χ^2 for 3:1 ^a
	R	S	Total	
Zhongguo 91/Huxuan 19	75	19	94	1.149
Huxuan 19/Zhongguo 91	53	20	73	0.224
Zhongguo 91/Shuangfeng 1	77	33	110	1.467
Shuangfeng 1/Zhongguo 91	121	39	160	0.033
Fengfeng/683 Nuo	99	41	140	1.371
683 Nuo/Fengfeng	82	31	113	0.357
Huxuan 19/Fengfeng	103	14	117	10.794**
Shuangfeng 1/Tetep	16	39	115	4.873**

^a** = significant difference at P <0.01 by χ^2 .

Reaction of rice cultivars from Ifugao Province, Philippines, to indigenous strains of the bacterial blight (BB) pathogen

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BB, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo), is endemic in the mountainous Ifugao Province, Philippines. All of the Xoo strains tested from Ifugao have been typed as race 5 on differential rice cultivars IR24 (carrying no resistance genes), IR20 (*Xa-4*), IR1545-339 (*xa-5*), DV85 (*xa-5* and *Xa-7*), and CAS209 (*Xa-10*).

Greater diversity has been recognized among race 5 strains based on DNA typing. We conducted this study to assess the reaction of traditional Ifugao rice cultivars to Ifugao Xoo strains representing different DNA types of race 5.

Strain PXO 80 was collected in 1975, PXO 112 in 1978, and PXO 154 in 1981 from Banaue, Ifugao. DNA analysis using the repetitive DNA probes pJEL101 and pTNX1 showed strains PXO 80 and PXO 112 as closely related, while PXO 154 was more distantly related. Viable seed of 361 accessions of traditional cultivars were obtained from the International Rice Germplasm Center, IRRI.

Three hills per cultivar were planted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in greenhouse plots

and arranged in rows according to accession number. Plants were inoculated with one each of the three Xoo strains at late maximum tillering stage using the clipping method. Lesion lengths and percent diseased leaf area were measured at 14 and 21 d after inoculation.

Nearly 9% of the accessions were either susceptible or highly susceptible to the three strains; 80% were moderately susceptible or susceptible; 1.7% were

dominant to moderate when varieties of each type were crossed (Table 1).

We analyzed segregation of F₂ according to expected values of a pair of genes and χ^2 test (Table 2). Six of the eight F₂ populations had segregation ratios of resistance that fit the expected values (P >0.05). The two other populations did not (P <0.01). □

moderately resistant to moderately susceptible, or resistant to moderately susceptible; several were moderately resistant to resistant; and a few showed differential reactions (Table 1).

To confirm the differential reactions observed, 32 selected accessions were again inoculated. Differential reactions were not confirmed for most of them because it appeared that some were from mixed seed.

Table 1. Accessions of traditional cultivars from Ifugao Province, Philippines, showing resistant (R) or moderately resistant (MR) reactions, and one accession showing differential reaction to three strains of Xoo from the Philippines.

Accession no.	Lesion length ^a (cm)			Rating
	PXO 80	PXO 112	PXO 145	
8035	1.36	7.92	10.36	R
8077	1.48	6.08	9.72	R
8111	1.41	5.91	8.82	R
8162	1.90	10.80	8.31	R
8164	1.04	10.32	11.60	R/MR
9134	1.18	14.12	8.78	R
11226	7.15	6.22	14.41	MR
11282	6.29	6.53	15.39	MR
11306	4.58	4.59	3.12	R
12060	2.44	3.21	10.15	R
23354	0.72	0.62	0.87	R
23362	13.10	10.10	25.27	MR
60611	1.28	3.56	7.07	R/MR
60613	2.89	6.018	20.00	R/MR
8106 (differential)	2.15	11.06	58.86	R/MR

^aAv of measurements from 2-5 leaves for each of 3 plants.

Table 2. Reaction of selected lines from Acc. 8106 to selected strains of Xoo representing different RFLP types.

Parental plant no.	Progeny tested (no.)	Reaction ^a to race 5 strains of Xoo			
		PXO 80	PXO 112	PXO 154	PXO 144
1	15	R	R	S	S
2	15	R	R	S	S
3	15	R	R	S	S
4	15	R	R	S	S
5	15	S	S	S	S

^aR: lesion lengths of 0-10.0 cm at 14 d after inoculation; S: lesion lengths greater than 20.0 cm at 14 d after inoculation.